

Experimental approach for assessing the impacts of intermittency: application on a 1 kW PEM electrolysis stack and on a 55 kW commercial PEM electrolyzer

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Hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a key player in the transition towards a cleaner energy future [1]. Sustainable hydrogen production can be effectively achieved through electrolysis, especially when powered by renewable energy sources. However, a significant challenge arises in integrating inherently intermittent renewable sources with industrial electrolyzers traditionally designed for steady-state operation. These fluctuations in electrical supply could markedly influence electrolyzer performance and durability. Despite the critical importance of understanding these effects, there is a notable shortage of experimental studies examining the impacts of intermittent operation on electrolyzer performance. Additionally, a recent literature review has put forward inconsistencies in the outcomes of existing studies, largely attributed to the absence of standardized testing protocols to rigorously assess the effects of intermittency on the performances of electrolyzers, both in the short-term and long-term [2].

To bridge this knowledge gap and to offer a comprehensive overview on the proposed methodology, this study introduces a novel experimental approach to evaluate both the short-term and long-term performance of proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysis technologies under intermittent conditions. Based on a stochastic framework that incorporates random intermittency around a specified operating point, test campaigns were performed on i) a 1 kW PEM electrolysis stack to investigate the long-term effects of intermittency and ii) a 55 kW industrial PEM electrolyzer to examine short-term impacts. This methodology entails comparing steady-state performance at a defined operating point with performance under random intermittent conditions, while keeping the average operating point constant. This approach isolates the influence of the operating point from the effects solely due to electrical input fluctuations. First results from the commercial electrolyzer revealed no short-term impacts of intermittent operation on the system key performance indicators i.e. the specific consumption or the final production purity. By providing deeper insights into the operational challenges and performance variations in PEM electrolyzers when integrated with renewable energy systems, the research advances the development of more resilient and adaptable hydrogen production technologies.

[1] International Energy Agency, « Global Hydrogen Review 2022 », 2022.

[2] E. Nguyen, P. Olivier, M.-C. Pera, E. Pahon, et R. Roche, « Impacts of intermittency on low-temperature electrolysis technologies: A comprehensive review », *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, vol. 70, p. 474-492, juin 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.ijhydene.2024.05.217.